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Experimental Physics

Spectrometry of Bi-207

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Abstract

Gamma and beta spectrometry are influential studies since they provide valuable insights to identify and quantify the presence of specific isotopes of radioactive elements. This information is beneficial in a wide variety of applications, especially in nuclear physics where it is used to study the properties of atomic nuclei, including the energy levels and decay modes of different isotopes. Other than that, they are properly used in medical imaging, environmental monitoring, and industrial and research applications. In this experiment, first, we studied the gamma spectrometry of Bi-207 with a Thallium-activated sodium Iodide detector (NaI(Tl)), and then it was complemented by its beta spectrometry that was observed using a semiconductor detector.

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1 Experiment 01: γ Spectrometry of Bi-207

1.1 Introduction

1.1.1 Purpose of the Experiment

The aim of this experiment is to achieve the gamma (γ) spectroscopy study of Bi-207 using a Thallium-activated sodium Iodide detector (NaI(Tl)).

Gamma is the photon of electromagnetic radiation emitted by the nuclei. It is massless, and its emission does not change the atomic number or the mass number of the parent nucleus, only the excitation energy of the nucleus decreases. This energy is carried by the emitted gamma during the de-excitation of the nucleus.

1.1.2 Process of emission and detection

Gamma radiation emitted from the source interacts with the crystal of the NaI scintillator, transferring all or part of its energy to the electrons of the crystal. This causes the excitation and de-excitation of the atoms of the crystal, releasing photons in the visible range. These photons are able to remove an electron from the photocathode of the PM through Photoelectric effect, which is then accelerated due to the potential difference in the dynodes. As it gains kinetic energy, a number of electrons are removed from the dynodes. The amplitude of the measured signal on the anode of PM is directly proportional to the incident gamma. This signal goes through preamplification and amplification before the final signal is displayed as a spectrum on the computer.

1.2 Experimental Setup

The experimental setup consists of the NaI(Tl) detector, photomultiplier tube (PM), Preamplifier (PA), Amplifier, Oscilloscope, Voltage source, and an acquisition system (Computer with Root software). The connection is as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: This figure shows the schematic diagram of the apparatus of the experiment. Image source: [1]

The voltage source was set to 700 Volts. To ensure that the system was working properly and that the settings were good, the oscilloscope was used to monitor the response of the setup at every step. It was also used to select the correct gain (amplification) for the experiment so that all the spectral peaks were well fit within the defined scale. Cesium-137, Cobalt-60 and Sodium-22 sources were used to calibrate the detectors. The calibration is necessary because there is no direct way to determine the exact energy values of the gamma radiation. These sources are relatively easy to work with and have known gamma decay energies. Therefore, determining the energies of the gamma radiation is possible. The gamma ray interacts with the crystal of the NaI scintillator by one of the following processes: Photoelectric effect, Compton effect, and pair production.

1.3 Results and Discussion

1.3.1 Recorded Data

The recorded data for each of the peaks of the observed spectra are given in the appendix (See "The recorded data for each peak of the spectra").

a) Cs - 137 (See table 13)

- b) Co - 60 (First peak) (See table 14)
- c) Co - 60 (Second peak) (See table 15)
- d) Na - 22 (First Peak) (See table 16)
- e) Na - 22 (Second Peak) (See table 17)

1.3.2 Observed Spectra

For Cs-137, as shown in Figure 2, one peak correspondent to the photoelectric effect, one correspondent to the Compton effect, and one peak corresponding to the back-scattering effect were observed (see Table 1 for more information).

Figure 2: This figure shows the gamma spectrum of Cs.

For Co-60, as shown in Figure 3, two peaks correspondent to the photoelectric effect, one correspondent to the Compton effect, and one peak corresponding to the back-scattering effect were observed (see Table 1 for more information).

For Na-22, as shown in Figure 4, one peak correspondent to the photoelectric effect, one correspondent to the Compton effect, and one peak corresponding to the back-scattering effect were observed (see Table 1 for more information). Additionally, we observed another

Figure 3: This figure shows the spectrum of Co.

peak corresponding to the beta annihilation (will be discussed in ["The analysis of Na - 22 spectrum"](#)).

Figure 4: This figure shows the spectrum of Na.

1.3.3 Analysis of the spectra

Table 1 shows the associated channel number of the different structures of the observed spectra.

Peaks	Na - 22	Cs - 137	Co - 60
Photoelectric effect	4.64702×10^5	2.48672×10^5	$4.28577, 4.85756 \times 10^5$
Compton effect	3.52324×10^5	1.6081×10^5	3.26259×10^5
Backscatter	1.94171×10^5	7.70478×10^4	8.69932×10^4

Table 1: This table shows the associated channel number of the different structures.

The characteristics of the photoelectric peaks (in channels)

Table 2 illustrates the position, FWHM, and number of events detected in each of the photoelectric effects peaks, in terms of channel numbers.

Peaks	Cs	Na (2nd)	Co (1st)	Co (2nd)
Position	2.48672×10^5	4.64702×10^5	4.28577×10^5	4.85756×10^5
FWHM	7.58988×10^3	1.24941×10^4	1.01707×10^4	1.19483×10^4
Number of events	122911824	6749513	18113859	17802128

Table 2: This table shows the position, FWHM, and Number of events detected in each of the photoelectric effects peaks, in terms of ADC channel values.

1.3.4 The analysis of Na - 22 spectrum

Figure 4 portrays the observed spectrum of Na - 22. Note that the spectrum of sodium -22 has a photoelectric peak at ADC of 4.64702×10^5 , emitted from a metastable Neon -22 after sodium decay. The peak corresponds to the total energy (1357 keV) in the events where all the energy of the incident gamma is dissipated in the crystal of the NaI scintillator. It also shows an annihilation peak at ADC of 1.9417×10^5 , corresponding to an energy of 545 keV which is the rest mass of an electron. Hence, it can be deduced that this peak is due to pair production. A part of the gamma energy is lost to produce electron-positron pairs.

The remaining gamma energy is given to the pairs as kinetic energy. The two particles can cause an annihilation in the vicinity of the detector, each producing a photon of energy 511 keV (theoretical value).

1.3.5 The Calibration curve

The calibration curve MeV/ channel was plotted by considering the gamma energy of the three sources used in the experiment as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: This figure shows the calibration curve. The observed data was fitted with a linear polynomial function $y = ax + b$, with $a = 0.003 \pm 0$ and $b = -37 \pm 2$.

1.3.6 The correspondence of the observed peaks to the calculated energies

Peaks	Cs	Co (1st)	Co (2nd)	Na (1st)	Na (2nd)
Calculated Energy (keV) [± 2 keV]	709	1249	1420	545	1357

Table 3: This table shows the calculated energies of the observed peaks after the calibration curve fitting. (Please note that the energy values have been adapted with respect to the error analysis discussed in Section "Uncertainty of energy measurement").

Table 4 indicates the calculated energies for the photoelectric peaks, compton edges, and backscattering effect (Please note that the energy values have been adapted with respect to the error analysis discussed in Section "Uncertainty of energy measurement").

Peaks	Na - 22	Cs - 137	Co - 60
Photoelectric effect (keV) [± 2 keV]	1357	709	1249, 1421
Compton effect (keV) [± 2 keV]	1020	446	942
Backscatter (keV) [± 2 keV]	546	194	224

Table 4: This table shows the associated energy values of the different structures.

1.3.7 The measurement of the background radiation

The background spectrum is visualized (in red color) in Figure 6, whereas the spectrum of Bi-207 is also presented. The measurement was taken for approximately 30 minutes for both. We observed three main peaks in the background spectrum. The observed energies for the peaks are presented in Table 5.

The presence of cosmic rays in the environment, the radioactive material present in human body, the walls are major reasons for the observed background radiation. Additionally, there were other radioactive material present in the laboratory which could possibly account for the background radiation.

Peak	1	2	3
Calculated Energy (keV) [± 2 keV]	71	629	1531

Table 5: This table shows the calculated energies of the observed peaks in the background spectrum. (Please note that the energy values have been adapted with respect to the error analysis discussed in Section "Uncertainty of energy measurement").

Figure 6: This figure shows the spectrum of Bi-207 (Blue) together with the measurement of the background radiation (red). The measurement was taken for approximately 30 minutes for both.

1.3.8 Energy resolution

The energy resolution is defined as shown in Equation 1 and note that the FWHM (ΔE) is approximated by the quantity of 2.35σ .

$$R = \frac{\Delta E}{E} \simeq \frac{2.35\sigma}{E} \quad (1)$$

Then the following relationship given in Equation 2, was used to determine a fitting curve as shown in Figure 7.

$$R(E) = \frac{K'}{\sqrt{E}} \quad (2)$$

Figure 7: This figure shows the behavior of the resolution values against the energy values of the observed five main peaks in the three spectra.

The value of the resolution associated with a gamma ray of 1 MeV was determined as 0.063 using the fitted curve.

1.3.9 The efficiency coefficient (α)

The detection efficiency is defined as given in Equation 3. Then the detection efficiency at a given energy $\varepsilon(E_1)$ can be defined as shown in Equation 4.

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\text{Number of } \gamma \text{ detected}}{\text{Number of } \gamma \text{ emitted}} \quad (3)$$

$$\varepsilon(E_1) = \frac{N_{obs}}{N_{expecied}} = \frac{N_1}{N_{Na22}B_{R1}} \quad (4)$$

Then the same situation can be considered for $\varepsilon(E_2)$, and then Equation 5 was obtained.

$$\frac{\varepsilon(E_1)}{\varepsilon(E_2)} = \frac{N_1 B_{R2}}{N_2 B_{R1}} \quad (5)$$

Also, the efficiency ratio can be defined as given in Equation 6.

$$\frac{\varepsilon(E_1)}{\varepsilon(E_2)} = \left(\frac{E_1}{E_2}\right)^\alpha \quad (6)$$

Using Equation 5, and Equation 6, the α value was determined as -0.94 ± 0.01 . (Please note that the value for α has been adapted with respect to the error analysis discussed in Section "Uncertainty of efficiency coefficient").

1.3.10 Bi - 207 spectrum

The energy spectrum of gamma emitted by Bi - 207 source is shown in Figure 8.

1.3.11 Analysis of the Bi - 207 spectrum

The energies of gamma rays observed are presented in Table 6.

Peak Number	1st	2nd	3rd
Channel Values	2.15803×10^5	3.91254×10^5	6.37508×10^5
Energy (keV) [± 2 keV]	611	1137	1876
Number of events	45613671	19037324	1058171

Table 6: The energies of the observed gamma rays. (Please note that the energy values have been adapted with respect to the error analysis discussed in Section "Uncertainty of energy measurement").

Figure 8: This figure shows the energy spectrum of gamma rays emitted by Bi - 207 source.

1.3.12 Relative intensities

We have to consider the relative intensity of this study since the photons are emitted in all directions and we only consider the number of photons incident on the detector. To negate the effect of solid angle, the below derivation is followed. The intensity of an arbitrary peak can be written as Equation 7. In the following derivation I represents the intensity, ρ represents the energy density, A is the area, t represents time, σ is the FWHM, and H is the height of the peak of the Gaussian model.

$$I = \frac{\rho}{A} = \frac{E}{tA} \quad (7)$$

Then we define the relative intensity between the first two peaks in the following way.

$$\frac{I_1}{I_2} = \frac{E_1}{tA_1} \times \frac{tA_2}{E_2} = \frac{E_1A_2}{E_2A_1} \quad (8)$$

Let's consider the area under the Gaussian distribution. The Gaussian function $f(x)$

can be introduced as shown in Equation 9.

$$f(x) = \frac{A}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left(-\frac{(x - \mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \quad (9)$$

Then at the peak value ($x = \mu$), the above function reduces in the following way.

$$f(x = \mu) = H = \frac{A}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} \quad (10)$$

Subsequently, A is given by Equation 11.

$$A = \sqrt{2\pi} \times \sigma H \quad (11)$$

Then combining with Equation 8, the following equation can be derived.

$$\frac{I_1}{I_2} = \frac{E_1 H_2 \sigma_2}{E_2 H_1 \sigma_1} \quad (12)$$

The relative intensities (with respect to peak 3) are presented in Table 7.

Relative intensity	First peak	Second peak	Third peak
Value	0.2243 ± 0.0002	0.034 ± 0.001	1 ± 0.04

Table 7: This table shows the relative intensity calculated for the observed three peaks with respect to the third peak. (Please note that the values have been adapted with respect to the error analysis discussed in Section "Uncertainty of relative intensities")

1.3.13 Branching ratios

The branching ratios for the three peaks were calculated using Equation 5, and 6 and the determined values are presented in Table 8.

To confirm the consistency, we need to calculate the ratios between the intensities of the three peaks. The intensity ratios are presented in Table 9.

Branching ratio	$\frac{B_{R2}}{B_{R1}}$	$\frac{B_{R3}}{B_{R2}}$	$\frac{B_{R3}}{B_{R1}}$
Value	4.30	28.84	124.07

Table 8: This table shows the branching ratios calculated for the observed three peaks.

Intensity ratio	$\frac{I_2}{I_1}$	$\frac{I_3}{I_2}$	$\frac{I_3}{I_1}$
Value	4.43	29.67	131.57

Table 9: This table shows the intensity ratios calculated for the observed three peaks.

Comparing Table 9 with Table 8, it is clear that the branching ratios are consistent with the previous measurements of relative intensities.

1.3.14 Compton edges and back-scattering peaks of Bi-207 spectrum

Table 10 checks the calculated energy values of the Compton edges and back-scattering peaks observed in the Bi-207 spectrum.

Peak	Back-scattering	Compton (1)	Compton (2)	Compton (3)
Calculated Energy (keV) [± 2 keV]	195	381	853	1554

Table 10: This table shows the calculated energies of the observed structural peaks in the Bi-207 gamma spectrum. (Please note that the energy values have been adapted with respect to the error analysis discussed in Section "Uncertainty of energy measurement").

2 Experiment 02: Beta Spectrometry of Bi-207

2.1 Introduction

2.1.1 Purpose of the experiment

The purpose of this experiment is to complement the γ spectroscopy experiment by observing the conversion electrons coming from the internal conversion process competing with γ emission with the semiconductor junction detector.

2.1.2 Process of emission and detection

Electrons revolve around the nucleus at discrete energy levels known as orbitals. These electrons can absorb the gamma radiation from the nucleus and escape the binding energy of the nucleus and become free electrons. The K shell electrons closest to the nucleus have a high probability of absorbing γ than those at a higher energy level. Therefore, electrons that are released from the K shell will have a higher intensity than those in the L shell. These two shells dominate this kind of transition, hence, the expectation is to see two peaks dominating in the resulting spectrum. The difference in energy between the emitted γ and the binding energy becomes the angular momentum of the electron. This process is known as internal conversion.

The internal conversion goes through a similar process. A semiconductor junction detector is used in this case because it is very sensitive to charged particles (electrons). This makes it a highly efficient detector because it does not read charge-less particles such as gamma.

2.2 Experimental Setup

In this experiment, a semi-conductor junction detector is used to detect electrons and it has no efficiency to γ radiation. They are usually known to have better energy resolution

(will be verified later in this experiment). The emitted charged particles from the source are responsible for creating electron-hole pairs inside the material, and the detection signal from the semiconductor is generated with the continuous collection of the electron-hole pairs. Si (with a band gap of 1.12 eV) is widely used for charged particle detectors whereas Ge (with a band gap of 0.661 eV) is used for gamma-ray spectroscopy.

2.3 Results and Discussion

2.3.1 Bi-207 β Spectrum

Figure 9: This figure shows the beta spectrum of Bi-207.

2.3.2 The positions of the peaks

Figure 10 shows the zoomed visualization of the two K-peaks of the Beta spectrum of Bi-207 whereas Table 11 shows the channel value and the corresponding energy value of the two peaks.

Figure 10: This figure shows zoomed two K-peaks of the Beta spectrum of Bi-207

Position	1st Peak	2nd Peak
ADC channel value	2.30805×10^5	4.77258×10^5
Energy value (keV) $[\pm 1 \text{ keV}]$	484	977

Table 11: This table shows the associated channel number of the different K peaks observed in the spectrum and their energy values (after the calibration). (Please note that the energy values have been adapted with respect to the error analysis discussed in Section "Uncertainty of energy measurement").

2.3.3 The Calibration Curve

The gamma transition energies of Bi-207 are 0.57 MeV and 1.06 MeV. Then the binding energy values of the K-shell and L-shell for Bi-207 were used to plot the calibration curve after determining the energies of the emitted electrons as shown in Figure 11.

2.3.4 Comparison of the energy resolution

The energy resolution FWHM (ΔE) for the K peak corresponding to 1.06 MeV was determined as 0.016. It is much lower than the one observed with NaI-PM (0.063) in the gamma spectrometry experiment. It indicates that the semi-conductor detector has a higher energy resolution which promises better accuracy of the measurements.

Figure 11: This figure shows the calibration curve for the Beta spectrum of Bi-207. The observed data was fitted with a linear polynomial function $y = ax + b$, with $a = 0.002 \pm 0$ and $b = 23 \pm 1$.

2.3.5 Ratios between alpha values

The measurements of α_K and α_L are significant to find spins and parities of the levels. α_i is defined as the probability of emitting an electron from layer (i) to the emission of gamma from the nuclei as presented in Equation 13.

$$\alpha_i = \frac{N_e}{N_\gamma} \quad (13)$$

The ratios $\frac{\alpha_K}{\alpha_L}$ for the gamma transition energies 0.57 and 1.06 MeV were calculated as shown in Table 12.

Ratio	$\frac{\alpha_{K_1}}{\alpha_{L_1}}$	$\frac{\alpha_{K_2}}{\alpha_{L_2}}$
Value	2.400	2.053

Table 12: This table presents the the ratios $\frac{\alpha_K}{\alpha_L}$ for the gamma transition energies 0.57 and 1.06 MeV.

Then by using the curves presented in Figure E2.2 in [1], the multipolarity of the first transition (corresponding to 0.57 MeV) was derived as E_2 . Following the same strategy multipolarity of the second transition (corresponding to 1.06 MeV) was derived as E_4 .

3 Error Analysis

For an arbitrary function $z = f(x, y)$, with two parameters x , and y with uncertainties σ_x and σ_y respectively, the total uncertainty of z (σ_z), can be determined as shown in Equation 14.

$$\sigma_z^2 = \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial x}\right)^2 \sigma_x^2 + \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial y}\right)^2 \sigma_y^2 + 2 \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial x}\right) \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial y}\right) \sigma_{xy}^2 \quad (14)$$

For the entire duration of the experiment, we assumed that we are dealing with independent measurements. That reduces Equation 14 to Equation 15.

$$\sigma_z^2 = \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial x}\right)^2 \sigma_x^2 + \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial y}\right)^2 \sigma_y^2 \quad (15)$$

Additionally, the total uncertainty of a measurement depends not only on the statistical error but also on the systematic error as shown in Equation 16. The statistical error is usually calculated from the size of the sample. For example, Poisson statistics are used for small numbers of events, whereas Gaussian statistics are used for large numbers of samples from a single distribution.

$$\sigma_{total} = \sqrt{\sigma_{stat}^2 + \sigma_{sys}^2} \quad (16)$$

The statistical error is capable of tracking random fluctuations during the measurement, and as a general rule of thumb, this error type is reduced with a higher number of measurements. But on the other hand, systematic errors are not due to random measurements, but rather to account for the inevitable mistakes that may happen during the experiment (for example, the non-perfect instruments used in the study).

In this study, we assume that our systematic error is null so that the error analysis is much more straightforward.

3.1 Uncertainty of energy measurement

The energy values were determined after plotting the calibration curve, and subsequently using Equation 17, where y is the energy value in keV, x is the channel number, a is the gradient and b is the intercept.

$$y = ax + b \quad (17)$$

Then using Equation 15, we can write the following equation for the uncertainty of y .

$$\sigma_y^2 = \left(\frac{\partial y}{\partial a}\right)^2 \sigma_a^2 + \left(\frac{\partial y}{\partial b}\right)^2 \sigma_b^2 \quad (18)$$

But since $\sigma_a = 0$ (from the calibration curve) and $\frac{\partial y}{\partial b} = 1$, we get $\sigma_y = \sigma_b = \pm 2$ keV for [Experiment 01](#) and we get $\sigma_y = \sigma_b = \pm 1$ keV for [Experiment 02](#).

3.2 Uncertainty of efficiency coefficient

Using Equation 5, and Equation 6, Equation 19 can be derived to determine α .

$$\alpha = \frac{\ln\left(\frac{\sigma_1 A_1}{\sigma_2 A_2 \times 1.8}\right)}{\ln\left(\frac{E_1}{E_2}\right)} \quad (19)$$

Then by defining K as $K = \frac{1}{\ln\left(\frac{E_1}{E_2}\right)}$, and with respect to Equation 15, the following equation can be obtained to calculate the uncertainty of α . It was calculated as ± 0.01 .

$$\sigma_\alpha = K \sqrt{\left(\frac{\sigma_{\sigma 1}}{\sigma_1}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{\sigma 2}}{\sigma_2}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{A1}}{A_1}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{A2}}{A_2}\right)^2} \quad (20)$$

3.3 Uncertainty of relative intensities

Equation 12 was used to determine the relative intensity. With respect to Equation 15, the following equation can be obtained.

$$\sigma_{I_{13}} = I_{13} \sqrt{\left(\frac{\sigma_{E_1}}{E_1}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{H_3}}{H_3}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{\sigma_3}}{\sigma_3}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{E_3}}{E_3}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{H_1}}{H_1}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{\sigma_1}}{\sigma_1}\right)^2}$$

(21)

Using the calculated values for relative intensities, their uncertainties were calculated as, $\sigma_{I_{13}} = \pm 0.0002$, $\sigma_{I_{23}} = \pm 0.001$, $\sigma_{I_{33}} = \pm 0.04$.

4 Conclusions

The goal of this experiment was to achieve the gamma and beta spectrometry studies of Bismuth-207. In this experiment, Cesium-137, Sodium-22, and Cobalt-60 spectra were successfully used to plot a calibration curve through which the energy levels of the Bi-207 were determined.

The spectra of the three sources produced very good results when compared to their respective theoretical energy values. The photoelectric peaks of Cs-137, Na-22, and Co-60 showed very slight deviations from their respective theoretical energies, and as an average, the experimentally obtained energies showed a deviation of 6.84%.

The energy resolution values associated with beta spectrometry were identified to be much lower than the values observed with NaI-PM in the gamma spectrometry experiment. Therefore the semiconductor detectors can be suggested to have better results.

The efficiency coefficient related to the scintillation detector was determined as -0.94 ± 0.01 with a slight deviation (of 6%) to the expected value of -1 .

The energy values of the first three photoelectric peaks of Bi-207 were determined to be (611 ± 2) keV, (1137 ± 2) keV, and (1876 ± 2) keV respectively. The effect of the background radiation was investigated and three main peaks were also observed in the background spectrum. The presence of cosmic rays in the environment, the radioactive material present in the human body, and the walls was declared to be major reasons for the observations.

Studying the gamma spectrum of the Bi-207, it was observed that the branching ratios are consistent with the measurements of relative intensities which confirmed the accuracy of the obtained results.

Uncertainties in the measurements were discussed for both gamma and beta spectra of Bi-207 assuming that the systematic error is null so that the error analysis is much more straightforward.

5 Literature Cited

References

- [1] Carole Gaulard. Practical work: Spectrometry of Bi-207. [https://https://ecampus.paris-saclay.fr](https://ecampus.paris-saclay.fr). Accessed: 2022-12-12.

6 Appendix

6.1 Appendix A: The recorded data for each peak of the spectra

Variable	Value	Error
Constant (P_0)	6.46054×10^3	1.19756×10^1
Mean (P_1)	2.48672×10^5	1.16225×10^1
Sigma (P_2)	$7.58988e \times 10^3$	9.73226
P_3	5.83070×10^1	8.43627×10^1

Table 13: The recorded data for the peak of the Cs spectrum.

Variable	Value	Error
Constant (P_0)	7.10510×10^2	3.84368
Mean (P_1)	4.28577×10^5	5.06934×10^1
Sigma (P_2)	1.01707×10^4	7.27243×10^1
P_3	8.60119×10^1	2.19214

Table 14: The recorded data for the first peak of the Co spectrum.

Variable	Value	Error
Constant (P_0)	5.94396×10^2	2.99429
Mean (P_1)	4.85756×10^5	4.74682×10^1
Sigma (P_2)	1.19483×10^4	4.23243×10^1

Table 15: The recorded data for the second peak of the Co spectrum.

Variable	Value	Error
Constant (P_0)	1.74305×10^3	6.91127
Mean (P_1)	1.94171×10^5	2.30231×10^1
Sigma (P_2)	1.10648×10^3	2.04657×10^2
P_3	1.10648×10^2	8.74551×10^1

Table 16: The recorded data for the first peak of the Na spectrum.

Variable	Value	Error
Constant (P_0)	2.15515×10^2	1.79281
Mean (P_1)	4.64702×10^5	7.84931×10^1
Sigma (P_2)	1.24941×10^4	7.08425×10^1

Table 17: The recorded data for the second peak of the Na spectrum.

6.2 Appendix B: Observed peaks (Zoomed versions)

Figure 12: This figure shows the zoomed peak of the Cs spectrum

(a) The first peak

(b) The second peak

Figure 13: This figure shows zoomed peaks of the Co spectrum

(a) The first peak

(b) The second peak

Figure 14: This figure shows zoomed peaks of the Na spectrum